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Abstract

Deliverable D6.1 Engagement and exploitation strategy describes the initial plan for targeted stakeholder engagement and for each consultation channel described, including expert groups, sustainability roundtables, engagement with EU initiatives and, public consultation, and sets out the exploitation strategy.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) have the potential to transform healthcare by enhancing patient outcomes, improving clinical processes, and advancing personalised medicine. However, their adoption has been slower than anticipated, primarily due to the absence of standardised assessment methodologies. This lack of uniformity has created uncertainty about the effectiveness, economic viability, and overall value of DHTs. Currently, the processes for assessing and adopting these technologies differ significantly across countries, with few having Health Technology Assessment (HTA) frameworks specifically designed for digital health innovations.

The ASSESS DHT project seeks to address these challenges by developing a harmonised framework for evaluating DHTs across various healthcare systems. The aim is to establish a comprehensive and consistent approach to assessing the effectiveness, safety, and economic impact of these technologies, thereby facilitating their integration into diverse healthcare settings. To ensure the practical application of the proposed frameworks, ASSESS DHT is implementing a proactive engagement and exploitation strategy.

The engagement strategy of the ASSESS DHT project is designed to involve a wide range of stakeholders throughout the entire lifecycle of DHTs. This multi-layered approach includes expert feedback from industry professionals, policymakers, clinical experts, and patients, ensuring that the project benefits from diverse perspectives. Additionally, the strategy involves collaboration with existing EU initiatives through strategic partnerships, joint events, and shared resources, to enhance the project's visibility and impact. Annual sustainability roundtables will be held to gather feedback, validate results, and promote adoption across participating countries. Furthermore, a public consultation process will ensure that the frameworks are broadly accepted and applicable across different healthcare contexts, thereby facilitating the successful integration and long-term sustainability of DHTs within European healthcare systems.

The exploitation strategy includes a comprehensive mapping of the project's assets and individual partner exploitation plans. Additionally, the creation of the ASSESS DHT European Repository will serve as a resource for DHT developers and decision-makers across Europe. This repository will provide access to project outputs, such as instructional videos, training resources, research findings, and evidence of impact, supporting the continuous improvement and adoption of DHTs.

1 Introduction

Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) hold immense promise in transforming healthcare by improving patient outcomes, optimising clinical processes, and advancing personalised medicine. However, despite these potential benefits, the adoption of DHTs has been limited and slower than anticipated. One of the major obstacles to their widespread use is the lack of standardised assessment methodologies, which leads to uncertainty regarding their effectiveness, economic viability, and overall value. Currently, the processes for assessing and adopting DHTs differ considerably across countries, with only a few having Health Technology Assessment (HTA) frameworks specifically designed for digital health innovations.

The ASSESS DHT project aims to address these challenges by harmonising existing methodologies for evaluating DHTs across various healthcare systems. The objective is to develop a unified framework that offers a comprehensive and consistent approach to assessing the effectiveness, safety, and economic impact of DHTs. This harmonisation is expected to facilitate the integration of DHTs into diverse healthcare settings. To ensure the practical adoption of the proposed frameworks, ASSESS DHT is establishing a proactive engagement and exploitation strategy from the outset.

Chapter 2 provides a mapping and classification of relevant stakeholders based on the stages of lifecycle of DHTs, in order to inform the engagement strategy, which is presented as a multi-level approach in chapter 3. Chapter 4 presents the project's exploitation strategy which ensures that key project outputs are effectively disseminated, utilised, and sustained beyond the project duration.

2 Stakeholder mapping and classification

2.1 Stages in the lifecycle of DHTs

The main type of stakeholders ASSESS DHT is targeting can be grouped into five distinct groups: users, developers, researchers, governing bodies, and financiers. Each group plays an essential role in the development, adoption, and deployment of DHTs, contributing significantly to the achievement of the project's overarching objectives.

Understanding the lifecycle of DHTs is crucial for grasping the involvement of the identified stakeholder groups. Lifecycles in this context encompass several stages, each demanding active participation from various stakeholders to ensure the successful development and integration of DHTs. Therefore, it is imperative to understand both the stages themselves and how stakeholders interact within them to fully appreciate the roles they play in advancing DHTs from concept to widespread adoption.

Research and development

During this stage, new technologies are conceptualised, designed, and initially tested. The development of health technologies often begins within research institutions and other innovation hubs, where new ideas are generated and potential solutions to healthcare challenges are explored¹. However, one of the major obstacles in this stage is the gap between laboratory research and practical application, commonly referred to as the "valley of death"². This gap can impede the transition from bench research to clinical use due to inadequate planning, lack of early dialogue with regulators, and insufficient understanding of healthcare needs. Thus, addressing these challenges swiftly is essential to avoid unnecessary delays.

Stakeholders' groups involved in this stage:

- **Developers:** Industry, technology developers, and healthcare authorities who procure development services for DHTs.
- **Researchers:** Academic and research institutions, ethics committees and institutional review boards, professional associations and societies.

Market authorisation

This stage involves obtaining approval from regulatory agencies, such as the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and other relevant notified bodies. Many DHTs, particularly those functioning as medical devices, must obtain CE marking before they can be commercialised. The CE marking indicates that a product has met the necessary EU safety, health, and environmental protection standards. Achieving this certification often requires compliance with the specific requirements outlined in the EU Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) for medical devices³ or the In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR)⁴. Additionally, DHTs must comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), including the completion of Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) when necessary⁵. If the DPIA reveals such risks, consultation with national data protection authorities, as stipulated under Article 36(1) of the GDPR, may be required. Regulatory approval is a prerequisite for

¹ Gutiérrez-Ibarluzea, I., Chiumente, M., & Dauben, H. P. (2017). The Life Cycle of Health Technologies. Challenges and Ways Forward. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 8, 14.

² Roberts, S. F., Fischhoff, M. A., Sakowski, S. A., and Feldman, E. L. (2012). Perspective: Transforming science into medicine: how clinician scientists can build bridges across research's "valley of death". *Acad. Med.* 87, 266–270.

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R0745>

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/746/oj>

⁵ GDPR, Recital 84.

subsequent evaluations by HTA agencies, but it does not cover the assessment of economic factors or broader impacts on healthcare systems.

Stakeholders' groups involved in this stage:

- **Governing bodies:** National and regional health authorities, European data protection authorities, and Standards Development Organisations (SDOs).
- **Researchers:** Academic and research institutions (involved in submitting data for regulatory approval).

Health Technology Assessment (HTA)

Following market authorisation, a technology undergoes Health Technology Assessment (HTA), where national or regional HTA agencies evaluate it. HTA involves an in-depth review of the technology's clinical effectiveness, cost-effectiveness, and broader social and ethical implications in real-world settings. The objective of HTA is to determine whether the technology offers value relative to existing alternatives and whether it should be recommended for widespread use within the healthcare system⁶. HTA findings are critical for informing subsequent policy decisions, including whether the technology should be considered for reimbursement by healthcare payers.

Stakeholders' groups involved in this stage:

- **Governing bodies:** Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies, national and regional health authorities, and HTA HAG (Heads of Agencies Group).
- **Researchers:** Academic and research institutions (involved in generating real-world evidence and cost-effectiveness analysis).

Market integration

Once a DHT undergoes HTA, it progresses to the market integration stage, which includes both the reimbursement processes and, if suitable, the required investments by healthcare providers (HCP). Reimbursement processes involve determining whether healthcare payers, such as government health insurance programs or private insurers, will cover the cost of the technology for users and under what conditions. Reimbursement decisions are influenced by the HTA's findings on the technology's cost-effectiveness and overall value to the healthcare system⁷.

Concurrently, healthcare providers make decisions on resource allocation for implementing said DHT and scaling it within the healthcare system. These investment decisions are influenced by reimbursement policies but are made based on HCP-specific needs, resources, and strategic priorities⁸. While reimbursement makes a technology financially accessible to patients, investment plays a crucial role in equipping the healthcare system to deliver the technology effectively.

In this context, successful market integration means that the technology is financially accessible to patients and adequately supported within the healthcare infrastructure, paving the way for its widespread adoption in clinical practice.

Stakeholders' groups involved in this stage:

- **Financiers:** Ministries of health, national health insurance programs, health insurance companies, and government agencies.

⁶ <http://htaglossary.net/>

⁷ Prodan, A., Deimel, L., Ahlqvist, J., Birov, S., Thiel, R., Toivanen, M., Kolitsi, Z., & Kalra, D. (2022). Success factors for scaling up the adoption of digital therapeutics towards the realization of P5 medicine. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 9.

⁸ Gutiérrez-Ibarluzea, I., Chiumente, M., & Dauben, H. P. (2017). The Life Cycle of Health Technologies. Challenges and Ways Forward. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 8, 14.

- **Governing bodies:** National and regional health authorities (involved in the decision-making process).
- **Developers:** Industry (both in negotiating prices and reimbursement levels, and also supplying the technology and supporting its implementation)

Implementation and use

The final stage in the lifecycle of a health technology is its actual implementation and use in clinical practice. During this stage, the technology is integrated into healthcare delivery, and its effectiveness is monitored in real-world settings. The performance of the technology during this stage is vital as it provides data on its impact on patient outcomes and overall healthcare efficiency. Thus, continuous monitoring and evaluation during this stage can lead to adjustments in usage or even reconsideration of the technology's role in the healthcare system if it fails to deliver the expected benefits⁹. This stage also encapsulates the cumulative effects of all previous stages – development, regulation, reimbursement, and investment – manifesting in practical outcomes.

Stakeholders' groups involved in this stage:

- **Users:** Healthcare providers, patients, and caregivers (actively using the technology in clinical practice).
- **Governing bodies:** National and regional health authorities (monitoring usage and compliance).
- **Developers:** Industry (providing ongoing support and updates).
- **Researchers:** Academic and research institutions (continuing to study the impact of technology).

Figure 1. Lifecycle of DHTs and stakeholder's involvement

⁹ Gutiérrez-Ibarluzea, I., Chiumente, M., & Dauben, H. P. (2017). The Life Cycle of Health Technologies. Challenges and Ways Forward. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 8, 14.

2.2 Classification and relevance of stakeholders in the DHT ecosystem

The participation of several stakeholders across the various stages of a DHT lifecycle highlight the ecosystem's complexity and interdependence. To further explore how these stakeholders contribute to the development and adoption of DHTs, the classification and specific relevance of each group are examined below.

Users

The user group includes healthcare providers, patients, and caregivers who directly interact with DHTs. These stakeholders are the primary beneficiaries of improved DHTs and provide crucial real-world feedback on usability and clinical outcomes. It is essential to involve them in validating the practical efficacy of DHTs and verifying that these technologies meet clinical needs while improving patient care.

Stakeholders	Relevance to the ASSESS DHT
Healthcare providers Patients Caregivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary beneficiaries of improved DHTs. Provide real-world feedback on DHT usability and the clinical outcomes associated with its use.

Developers

Developers include industry players and healthcare authorities procuring DHT development services. This group drives innovation by creating solutions that meet market demands while aiding alignment with healthcare standards through collaboration with researchers and governing bodies. Overall, their role is essential in translating scientific research into practical applications.

Stakeholders	Relevance to the ASSESS DHT
Industry Healthcare authorities who procure development services for DHTs Technology developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drive innovation in DHTs, creating solutions that meet market demands. Ensure products align with healthcare standards through collaboration with researchers and governing bodies.

Researchers

Researchers encompass academic and research institutions, ethics committees and institutional review boards, and professional associations and societies. This group conducts rigorous studies to assess the efficacy of DHTs and provide evidence-based support for their adoption. Their methods and collaboration processes promote scientific rigour and validation, which is crucial for building trust in new technologies.

Stakeholders	Relevance to the ASSESS DHT
Academic and research institutions Ethics committees and institutional review boards Professional associations and societies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct research on DHT efficacy and provide evidence-based support for adoption. Innovate through academic collaboration, ensuring scientific rigor and validation.

Governing Bodies

The assessment and utilisation of DHTs are significantly influenced by governing bodies such as national and regional health authorities, HTA bodies, European data protection authorities, SDOs, HTA HAG, centres of excellence, and international organisations. These organisations facilitate the integration of DHTs into healthcare IT systems and address ethical, legal, data protection, cybersecurity, and compliance considerations conducive to the adoption.

Stakeholders	Relevance to the ASSESS DHT
National and regional health authorities Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies European data protection authorities Standards Development Organisations HTA HAG (Heads of Agencies Group) Centres of excellence International organisations that oversee assessment and utilisation of DHTs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shape HTA, interoperability, and funding frameworks, supporting the adoption and integration of DHTs within healthcare system IT infrastructures. • Address ethical, legal, data protection, cybersecurity, and compliance considerations, promoting a cohesive environment for DHT adoption. • Robust and transparent frameworks to send clear signals to innovators about how value in the field of DHT is assessed.

Financiers

Financiers include health ministries, national health insurance programs, and health insurance companies, which make evidence-based investment, procurement and reimbursement decisions for DHTs and, thus, facilitate patient access to innovative solutions. Additionally, financiers assess cost-effectiveness and benefits, supporting sustainable funding models.

Stakeholders	Relevance to the ASSESS DHT
Ministries of health National health insurance programs Health insurance companies Government agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence-based funding and reimbursement decisions for DHTs, facilitating patient access to innovative solutions. • Assess cost-effectiveness and benefits, supporting sustainable funding models. • Clear and robust processes to help innovators generate the necessary evidence to inform and navigate pricing and reimbursement processes.

3 Engagement strategy

The engagement strategy in ASSESS DHT includes a multi-layered, multi-stakeholder approach, designed to enable the gathering of comprehensive input and support from diverse groups that have been previously mapped and are essential to the project's success. This strategy involves four distinct levels of interaction, each with its specific objectives and outcomes:

Table 1. Engagement strategy overview

Interaction level	Stakeholder group(s)	Mode of interaction	Expected outcomes
Level 1: Expert feedback	Expert groups established by the project Digital health developers / industry Policy makers & regulators Clinical experts Patients/citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshops Interviews Draft reviews, commentaries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In-depth input on project specifics Real-time feedback on project development and implementation Continuous refinement of project outputs
Level 2: Synergies with EU Initiatives	EU projects, communities, and organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategic partnerships Joint events (conferences, seminars) Information and resources sharing Collaborative research and publications Shared communication and dissemination channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross-pollination of ideas and best practices Resource sharing and joint funding opportunities Enhanced visibility and network expansion Complementary project objectives
Level 3: Sustainability roundtables	Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies, national and regional health authorities, and HTA HAG (Heads of Agencies Group)	<p>Yearly roundtables (3 in total) with all EU27 + 16 associated countries.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year 1: inform Year 2: seek feedback and validate the project framework Year 3: Promote, endorse and adopt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategic guidance and alignment with national and EU-level policies Enhanced adoption and application of the ASSESS DHT framework Strengthening political and institutional support Securing endorsements and long-term sustainability of the project outcomes
Level 4: Public consultation	Open consultation with stakeholder groups (between M18 – M35)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online consultation 2-day consensus meeting with 10-12 stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feedback and validation of the proposed frameworks in the wider community

3.1 Expert feedback

The first level focuses on collecting detailed feedback from expert groups specifically formed for the project. These groups comprise digital health developers, industry professionals, policymakers and regulators, clinical experts, and patients/citizens. Interaction methods include workshops, interviews, and reviewing drafts and commentaries. The goal is to secure in-depth insights into project specifics, provide real-time feedback during development and implementation, and continuously refine the project's outputs based on expert advice.

Establishing the expert pool

To form a robust expert pool for the project that can be promptly engaged based on the needs of the different content-related work project partners are carrying out, a two-phased public open call approach is applied.

Phase 1 aimed at setting the foundation of the pool of experts by identifying them early on in the project. The call was launched on 18 March and had a specific deadline (cut-off) of 5 April 2024. The call was widely disseminated through social media, the project website, and partner networks.

Figure 2. Visual used in the social media campaign to disseminate the call for experts.

A call document was set up and published on the website. It included an introduction, outlining the purpose of soliciting expert input to develop and harmonise assessment frameworks for DHTs across Europe. It was structured into several key sections, detailing the project's goals and the importance of a multi-stakeholder approach; described the four categories of experts needed and the forms of participation and contribution, as well as the desired expert profile, specifying the qualifications (in the form of quality award criteria) sought for each group. The document also covered application details, provided guidelines for the application process, the quality award criteria used to assess applications, as well as the process of how applications will be assessed by an Expert Evaluation Committee (EAC).

The call attracted a total of 93 applications, out of which 86 experts were selected following a thorough evaluation of the quality award criteria by the EAC representatives from ASSESS DHT partners AIHTA, TUB, TUD, i-HD, FPS, and IDFE. Consortium partners were made available the profiles of the experts included in the expert pool.

Phase 2 is in the form of a continuous call without cut-off dates, whereas each new expert application is evaluated on its own when it is submitted. For this call, the call document was adapted accordingly,

by using award criteria generic to all types of stakeholder groups. The continuous call was launched on 25 June 2024.

The resulting pool of expert with their profile descriptions is available to the ASSESS DHT consortium in order to identify and organise specific expert input according to the needs of the project partners. Input can be organised, for example, in the form of tailored workshops, interviews, or other activities, with WP6 managing logistical and administrative tasks.

Annex I includes the Phase 1 and 2 call documents, as well as the outcome of the phase 1 evaluation. Updates on the pool and phase 2 expert additions will be reported in D6.2 and D6.5.

3.2 Synergies with EU initiatives

At the second level, ASSESS DHT seeks to establish synergies with existing EU initiatives by actively engaging with various projects, communities, and organisations within the EU. This engagement involves forming strategic partnerships, participating in joint events such as conferences and seminars, sharing information and resources, collaborating on research and publications, and utilising common communication and dissemination channels. The anticipated outcomes include the exchange of ideas and best practices, resource sharing, joint funding opportunities, enhanced visibility, expanded networks, and alignment of project objectives. This strategy will be implemented through an iterative process throughout the project:

- ASSESS DHT will conduct ongoing reviews of relevant EU initiatives related to DHTs, Health Technology Assessments (HTA), and associated fields. This will involve using resources like CORDIS and leveraging insights from project partners to identify initiatives that align with ASSESS DHT's goals. An initial list has already been developed and it includes projects such as EUCAPA¹⁰, REALM¹¹, CYCLOMED¹², CYMEDSEC¹³ and others – all relevant to ASSESS DHT due to intersections with topics such as HTA capacity building, MDR regulation or cybersecurity for digital medical devices.
- The project team will initiate contact with identified projects through formal communication channels. This process may include sending introductory emails, arranging virtual meetings, and presenting the objectives of ASSESS DHT along with potential areas for collaboration.
- ASSESS DHT will establish Memorandums of Understanding (MOUs) or informal agreements with selected projects. These agreements will clearly define the scope of collaboration, shared objectives, and mutual benefits, to create clarity in roles and expectations.
- The project will aim to organise and participate in joint conferences, seminars, and workshops, serving as platforms for knowledge exchange, addressing challenges, and identifying opportunities for joint research or resource sharing.

¹⁰ EUCAPA (<https://www.eucapa.eu/>) aims at providing patients and patient experts with the adequate knowledge and skills to effectively participate in the Health Technology Assessment (HTA) process.

¹¹ REALM (<https://realm-ai.eu/>) aims to develop a collaborative framework through which regulatory authorities, software developers, healthcare professionals and policy offers can jointly create and evaluate innovative medical device software – for the direct benefit of patients and healthcare practitioners.

¹² CYCLOMED (<https://www.cylcomed.eu/>) envisages strengthening the cybersecurity of connected, in vitro diagnostic, and software as medical devices, maintaining their performance and safety for patients and preserving or increasing exchanged private data confidentiality, integrity and availability.

¹³ CYMEDSEC (<https://cymedsec.eu/>) focuses on enhanced cybersecurity for networked medical devices through optimisation of guidelines, standards, risk management and security by design. The project fosters a dynamic interplay between novel technologies and regulatory frameworks, balancing safety with innovation. Focusing on the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), CYMEDSEC enhances cybersecurity across multiple layers for remote patient monitoring ('hospital at home') and critical care. The project innovates via regulatory review, cybersecurity oversight, new standards, and a benefit-risk toolbox to drive a secure and competitive healthcare sector.

- The project will seek opportunities to co-author research papers, reports, or policy briefs with partner projects. Collaborative research will focus on areas of mutual interest, such as the evaluation of DHTs, economic analyses, or policy development.
- The project will coordinate with partner initiatives to jointly disseminate research findings and project outcomes through shared publications, media releases, and presentations at international forums.

Collaboration with sister project EDiHTA

ASSESS DHT is one of two projects funded under the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-HLTH-2023-IND-06-07 - Development and harmonisation of methodologies for assessing digital health technologies in Europe, and tasked with address the methodological challenges of assessing DHTs, including their added value and health benefits for patients and the digital transformation of health systems. The sister project EDiHTA¹⁴, coordinated by Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, has similarities (e.g. it also started in January 2024, it involves HTA bodies, including a common partner NICE from the United Kingdom), but also differences (e.g. different project duration, whereas ASSESS DHT is planned as a three-year project and EDiHTA has four years) which imply that the two projects should align their activities and efforts, since they have a common overall aim and engage with similar stakeholders to a great extent.

This is the reason why both projects started collaborating early on (even before the project start), facilitated by the European Commission. Common areas of interest in which alignment of activities was deemed important include stakeholder engagement, dissemination, exchange on key scientific activities, and shared understanding of the piloting activities.

To ensure cross-project collaboration and alignment, the coordinators of the two project have established a set of monthly meetings, involving where necessary additional project partners on both sides.

This collaborative approach highlights the significance of stakeholder involvement in shaping the future of healthcare technology assessment. By pooling their resources, EDiHTA and ASSESS DHT aim to make a meaningful impact on the European HTA landscape, contributing to the sustainability and effectiveness of healthcare systems throughout Europe.

3.3 Sustainability roundtables

The third level of the engagement strategy prioritises sustainability through annual roundtables with HTA agencies. The Consortium of Heads of Agencies Group (HAG) has formed after the end of the EUnetHTA Joint Actions and the beginning of the implementation of the HTA Regulation and includes all HTA institutions in Europe. HAG and the Subgroup of the HTA Coordination Group on “voluntary cooperation” with the focus on the collaboration on assessments of DHT will be approached in early September to sign up for participation in the ASSESS DHT sustainability roundtables.

These roundtables are scheduled to take place over three years, with each year focusing on specific objectives. The first roundtable will take place virtually on 4 November 2024, for presentations on the aim and methodological approaches of ASSESS DHT and discussions on the expectations of HTA agencies on the emerging ASSESS DHT framework.

The second year will focus on gathering feedback and validating the project framework, ensuring it meets the needs and expectations of the involved parties. By the third year, the goal is to promote, endorse, and facilitate the adoption of the framework across participating countries. This phased

¹⁴ <https://edihta-project.eu/>

approach is designed to provide strategic guidance, enhance the uptake and practical application of ASSESS DHT assets, and bolster political and institutional support. Additionally, it aims to secure critical endorsements that will ensure the long-term sustainability and impact of the project across the European DHT landscape.

3.4 Public consultation

The fourth level involves an open public consultation targeting a wider range of stakeholder groups, scheduled between months 18 and 35 of the project. This process includes an open consultation on the project's website and a two-day consensus meeting with 10-12 stakeholders. The primary aims are to gather feedback the project may be able to incorporate to increase the acceptability of its outputs to their primary future users, and to validate the proposed frameworks within the broader community, ensuring their acceptance and applicability across different contexts.

Figure 3. Engagement timeline as described in the engagement strategy

Each year the project will engage external experts, will establish synergies with EU initiatives and carry out sustainability roundtables with HTA agencies to ensure uptake of the ASSESS DHT outputs, as well as organisation of a public consultation towards the second half of the project.

4 Exploitation strategy

The exploitation strategy for the ASSESS DHT project aims to ensure that the project's outputs are effectively disseminated, utilised, and sustained beyond its duration. This strategy is closely aligned with the communication and dissemination plan outlined in Deliverable D1.5, as well as the engagement strategy discussed in chapter 3. The primary objective is to maximise the impact of the project by ensuring that the tools and the methodologies developed are widely adopted and integrated into relevant sectors.

Mapping of key assets

A key element of this strategy involves the comprehensive mapping of ASSESS DHT assets. This mapping will provide a detailed inventory of the resources and capabilities generated by the project, allowing us to identify the most effective ways to leverage these assets for maximum impact. Technical assets include the tools, frameworks, and methodologies developed within the project. Knowledge assets comprise the research findings, best practices, and case studies produced. Collaborative networks refer to the partnerships and relationships established with stakeholders across the EU, while community engagement assets involve the involvement and feedback from the broader DHT community.

This mapping process will clarify what has been developed and how these resources can be applied in different contexts. It will also help identify any gaps or areas that require further development, ensuring that the exploitation strategy is both comprehensive and focused.

Exploitation plans of individual organisations

Given the diverse composition of the ASSESS DHT consortium, which includes HTA agencies, DHT manufacturers, research universities, institutes, and patient organisations, the exploitation strategy will address unique needs and opportunities within each organisation. Each consortium partner will develop its own exploitation plan, leveraging its specific strengths and positions within the DHT ecosystem.

For HTA agencies, the focus will be on integrating the ASSESS DHT manual and tools into their existing assessment processes, thereby enhancing their capabilities in evaluating digital health technologies.

DHT manufacturers will explore how evaluation pilot results can be used to enhance market opportunities. This could involve refining products based on pilot feedback or using evaluation outcomes to demonstrate the efficacy and safety of their technologies, thereby improving their market position.

Research universities and institutes will use the insights gained from the project to support ongoing and future research initiatives. The knowledge generated by ASSESS DHT can inform new research projects, contribute to academic publications, and support the development of new theories and methodologies in this domain.

Patient organisations will play a key role in enhancing the uptake of DHTs by ensuring that patient needs and perspectives are incorporated into the development and deployment of these technologies. Using the resources and frameworks developed by ASSESS DHT, these organisations can advocate more effectively for technologies that improve patient care and outcomes.

The ASSESS DHT European Repository

A central element of the exploitation strategy is the creation of the ASSESS DHT European Repository, hosted by partner I-HD. This repository will be a systematic, semantically indexed, and searchable database containing all the project's outputs, including instructional videos, training resources, research findings, and evidence of impact on health systems.

The repository is intended not just as a storage space, but as a dynamic resource to support DHT creators and decision-makers across Europe. It will foster a collaborative environment where DHT developers, HTA agencies, and other stakeholders can share insights, best practices, and challenges, thereby improving the quality and acceptability of future DHT applications.

This platform is needed for several purposes. These purposes effectively scope the requirements that the repository has to meet. The list below is a starting point for consultation with key stakeholders over the coming months, before work begins on a formal design specification for the repository.

- For HTA Bodies
 - To provide a protected discussion and information sharing platform where challenges about how to best assess innovative DHT functions and how best to evolve existing assessment methodologies in the face of new requirements and threats such as cyber security breaches, can be discussed and consensus be found.
 - To enable bodies to share experiences of assessment findings and decisions in a protected space so market can be tracked, cross-country differences can be explored, and alignment possibilities can be identified.
 - To codevelop and publish updates to methodologies, guidance, tools that can be shared across HTA bodies.
- For DHT developers
 - A platform to find resources that explain the requirements and criteria for DHT approval, per DHT category.
 - A protected forum to share pre-competitive experiences, challenges with preparing for and obtaining approvals.
- For all health stakeholders concerned
 - Resources that explain the quality criteria that health systems require in order to approve digital health technologies.
 - Evidence of health outcomes and healthy economic benefits from the use of DHT.
 - Horizon scanning DHT innovations and what benefits and assurance stakeholders should expect of their quality and trustworthiness.

Future implementation and sustainability

Beyond the immediate project timeline, ASSESS DHT will focus on the long-term sustainability and implementation of its frameworks. The sustainability roundtables, discussed earlier, will serve as a platform to address barriers to implementation, explore enablers, and identify future funding opportunities and partnerships. Recommendations for the future implementation will also be derived, ensuring they remain relevant and adaptable to the evolving DHT landscape. These recommendations will be informed by ongoing feedback from stakeholders and the insights gained from the project's activities.

The progress and outcomes of the engagement and exploitation strategy set out in this deliverable will be documented in the following deliverables: D6.2, the Interim Report on Engagement, Consultation, Exploitation, and Sustainability Actions, due in Month 24, and D6.5, the Final Report on Engagement, Exploitation, and Sustainability, due in Month 36.

Annex I: Expert pool – call documents and assessment

Phase 1 call document

empirica **iHD** The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data **A** Fundación Pública Andaluza Progreso y Salud Consejería de Salud y Consumo **TU** TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DRESDEN

NICE National Institute for Health and Care Excellence **ainta** **TLV** **International Diabetes Federation Europe** **ULB** UNIVERSITÉ LIBRE DE BRUXELLES

TU **bettercare** **Tech4Care** **HEARTKINETICS**

Project acronym: ASSESS DHT
Grant Agreement Number: 101137347
Project full title: Development and harmonisation of methodologies for assessing digital health technologies in Europe
Website: www.assess-dht.eu

Call for Experts

Funded by the European Union

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1 Call for expert input in the development of assessment frameworks for Digital Health Technologies

This call focuses on the importance of increasing the adoption of trustworthy and effective Digital Health Technologies (DHT) across Europe. To develop and harmonise methodologies for assessing DHTs in Europe, a multi-stakeholder perspective needs to be adopted, to ensure that the resulting methodologies and approaches are fit for purpose and address the real needs of all those involved.

ASSESS DHT (Development and harmonisation of methodologies for assessing digital health technologies in Europe) is looking to engage with external experts on a continuous basis by communicating specific requests for input to the project work in advance, to which the experts can respond depending on their availability. Expert contributions will be remunerated.

What is ASSESS DHT

ASSESS DHT is a European project running from January 2024 to December 2026 that aims to boost the adoption of reliable DHTs across Europe, contributing towards a unified digital single market for healthcare systems and patients to access DHTs and establishing a strong European market. The project will develop a novel assessment framework, surpassing existing models, to ensure consistent Health Technology Assessment (HTA) adoption throughout Europe and addressing emerging challenges in areas such as Digital Therapeutics, Artificial Intelligence, and telehealth.

ASSESS DHT is implemented by a consortium comprising 14 partners from 7 countries representing HTA, research organisations, DHT companies, professional and patient organisations as well as intergovernmental and multi-stakeholder associations at EU, Member State, and regional level.

More information about the project can be found at www.assess-dht.eu.

1.1 Expert groups called to inform, develop, and harmonize methodologies

We want to **establish expert groups** comprising different viewpoints, which are engaged in various activities to help inform the development and harmonisation of the proposed methodologies.

ASSESS DHT has an ambitious workplan spanning three years covering a plethora of activities related to consolidation of existing knowledge and materials, development of new approaches, tools, and manuals for assessing DHT, testing and validation of those approaches, and setting the ground for wider uptake and sustainability of the project work.

The input of external stakeholders is seen as crucial for the success of the project, especially so for the first project year which foresees very intensive development, which would strongly benefit from co-creation and expert knowledge.

ASSESS DHT foresees the creation of four expert groups (EGs):

1. EG1: Digital health developers/industry
2. EG2: Policy makers & regulators
3. EG3: Clinical experts
4. EG4: Patients/citizens

1.2 How to contribute

The input may be in the form of participation in an online event (e.g. a two-hour webinar), provision of written feedback to a draft shared document, participation in an online interview, etc. It is not foreseen that experts will be required to travel physically.

It is expected that experts are provided with a reasonable number of requests spanning the project timeline, for example 4 requests in 2024, 2 requests each in 2025 and 2026, but not for more than 6-8 requests in total.

ASSESS DHT has reserved budget for remunerating experts. Specific budget lines are agreed based on the specific assignment at hand, and usually vary between 50 € and 400 €.

The budget poses limitations, therefore in case of a significant number of approved applications (i.e. extending to more than the 6-8 requests foreseen), the evaluation scores of the applications will form a ranking to represent a priority list for engagement (a pool of experts). In this sense, a successful application is not a guarantee for a definite request for a given expert.

1.3 Desired expert profile

Depending on the expert group, ASSESS DHT is looking for experts according to the short profiles below. It is important to note that the experts are individuals, representatives of a stakeholder group.

Digital health developers/industry

Digital health developers/industry have a crucial role in identifying healthcare systems and end-user needs and shaping the design, development, and deployment of DHTs. Their input is vital because they possess expertise in technology innovation, user experience, and market dynamics, ensuring that DHTs are both technically feasible and commercially viable. Additionally, their insights can help address potential barriers to adoption and scalability, ultimately improving the effectiveness and accessibility of digital health solutions.

Policy makers & regulators

Policy makers and regulators play critical role in establishing the legal and regulatory framework governing the use of DHTs. Their input is important to ensure that DHTs meet stringent standards for safety, efficacy, and data privacy, safeguarding public health and trust. Moreover, their decisions can influence reimbursement policies, market access, and interoperability standards, shaping the broader landscape for digital health innovation and adoption.

Clinical experts

Such experts bring valuable insights into the practical application of DHTs within health and care settings. Their input is crucial for assessing the clinical validity, utility, and integration of DHTs into existing workflows and care pathways. By leveraging their expertise in medical practice, evidence-based medicine, and patient care, clinical experts can help optimise DHTs and DHT assessment processes to better meet the needs of healthcare providers and improve patient outcomes.

Patients/citizens

Citizens, patients, and caregivers are the ultimate end-users and beneficiaries of DHTs. Their input is essential for ensuring that DHTs are user-centred, culturally sensitive, and responsive to diverse healthcare needs and preferences. By actively involving patients and citizens in the assessment and design process, stakeholders can enhance the usability, acceptability, and relevance of DHTs, fostering greater engagement, empowerment, and satisfaction with healthcare delivery and outcomes.

We are particularly inviting individuals with good, generic knowledge of patient and carer agency in a broad array of health and care areas that are subject to digital transformation. They should ideally have experience in co-creating services together with innovators, have participated in digital health services design and design validation as well assessment and evaluation of health technologies. They would also typically actively participate in their own prevention, health maintenance and care planning in close cooperation with their physicians.

2 How to apply

The call is open to natural persons able to participate in the envisaged requests for input as outlined in section 1.3. If an applicant has relevant experience suitable for representing more than one of the four expert groups, the most suited group should be prioritised (applications for multiple groups are not allowed).

2.1 Application process and deadline

Interested parties are required to submit their applications electronically by submitting a filled in application online form. The different forms are:

- Application form ASSESS DHT Expert Group 1: Digital health developers / industry: [Link](#)
- Application form ASSESS DHT Expert Group 2: Policy makers & regulators: [Link](#)
- Application form ASSESS DHT Expert Group 3: Clinical experts: [Link](#)
- Application form ASSESS DHT Expert Group 4: Patients/citizens: [Link](#)

The forms must be completed in English.

The deadline for application is ~~29 March~~ 5 April 2024 17:00 CET.

Any questions about the call must be sent to applications-assess-dht@empirica.com before ~~20 March~~ **2 April 2024**. Answers will be made available at <https://assess-dht.eu/call-experts/> by **3 April 2024**.

2.2 Evaluation process

The ASSESS DHT coordinator will appoint an Expert Evaluation Committee (EEC) consisting of experts from the ASSESS DHT consortium.

Members of the EEC are appointed in their personal capacity. After application deadline, the ASSESS DHT coordinator will provide the EEC members with access to the submitted applications. The EEC will read the applications and score them based on the award criteria scorecard below. Each EEC member provides a score for each award criterion. A final joint decision is reached by a simple majority vote in a dedicated EEC meeting chaired by the ASSESS DHT coordinator. Applications must score above the thresholds given, for each threshold. Applications that do not reach the minimum quality thresholds (individual and totals) will be rejected.

The following award criteria will be used:

Award criteria	Maximum points	Threshold
Applications by digital health developers / industry		
Evidenced level of experience related to developing DHTs	5	2
Evidenced level of experience and knowledge of technological trends, innovation processes, and market dynamics in the healthcare sector	5	2
Experience with and knowledge of regulatory requirements, data privacy considerations, and industry standards for digital health solutions	5	n.a.
Experience with communication skills and an ability to articulate the perspectives and needs of the stakeholder group you represent	5	n.a.
Total maximum for applications by digital health developers / industry	20	10
Applications by Policy makers & regulators		
Evidenced experience with working in (European or national)	5	2

Award criteria	Maximum points	Threshold
governmental or regulatory bodies responsible for digital healthcare policy, legislation, or oversight		
Evidenced experience and knowledge in health law, policy analysis, public health administration or other relevant experience with a focus on digital health and medical technology policy and regulation	5	2
Evidenced experience (if any) and familiarity with international standards, guidelines, and best practices for evaluating and regulating digital health technologies	5	n.a.
Total maximum for applications by policy makers & regulators	15	6

Applications by clinical experts		
Extent of professional experience in the healthcare sector	5	2
Evidenced experience and knowledge in clinical practice, research, education, or healthcare leadership roles	5	2
Relevant references and publications	5	n.a.
Total maximum for applications by clinical experts	15	6

Applications by patients/citizens		
Extent of interest in the topic of digital health technology	5	n.a.
Evidence of relevant lived experience as patient or caregiver having used or desired to use digital health technology for their or others' health needs	5	n.a.
Evidenced ability to articulate the perspectives, preferences, and priorities of the patient/citizen community regarding the use of digital health technologies, including accessibility, usability, and privacy concerns	5	n.a.
Total maximum for applications by clinical experts	15	6

A five-point system is defined as:

1. *Insufficient* (fails to address the criterion under examination or the criterion cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information).
2. *Poor* (the criterion is addressed in an inadequate manner, or there are serious inherent weaknesses or gaps in expected information).
3. *Fair* (while the criterion is broadly addressed, there are some weaknesses to it or gaps in expected information).
4. *Good* (the criterion is addressed well, although improvements or further information would have been highly desirable).
5. *Very good* (the criterion is addressed well, although certain improvements or additional information are still possible).
6. *Excellent* (all relevant aspects of the criterion are successfully addressed; any shortcomings are minor).

In case of a conflict of interest identified by an EEC member, he/she will immediately notify the ASSESS DHT coordinator and will withhold from providing an evaluation for that particular application.

Based on the scores, applicants will be informed of the outcome of the evaluation (i.e. whether they have been selected (above threshold) and under what rank/prioritisation).

2.3 Expert remuneration and conditions

ASSESS DHT has reserved budget for remunerating experts. Specific budget lines are agreed based on the specific assignment at hand, and usually vary between 50 € and 400 €. Assignments and conditions are agreed between the ASSESS DHT coordinator and the expert via email.

The budget poses limitations, therefore in case of a significant number of approved applications (i.e. extending to more than the 6-8 requests foreseen), the evaluation scores of the applications will form a ranking to represent a priority list for engagement (a pool of experts). In this sense, a successful application is not a guarantee for a definite request for a given expert.

Phase 1 assessment

Applications were assessed by an Expert Evaluation Committee (EAC), with representatives from ASSESS DHT partners AIHTA, TUB, TUD, i-HD, FPS, and IDFE. Based on the 93 applications received, WP6 and T6.1 lead empirica allocated assessors from these organisations to individual applications, ensuring each application is assessed by two individuals. Assessors provided their preliminary scores for the quality award criteria. These scores were discussed with the concerned assessors as part of a consensus meeting with EAC members organised by empirica on 30 April 2024. During the meeting, scores were discussed with the assessors concerned until agreement on the final scores was reached.

Due to GDPR considerations and the fact that this deliverable is in the public domain, the names and organisations of the experts are not listed. Details can be provided to the European Commission upon request.

Phase 2 call document

<https://assess-dht.eu/assess-dht-pool-of-experts-application>

ASSESS DHT Pool of experts

In addition to the open call for experts in March 2024, which resulted in the setting up of the ASSESS DHT pool of experts, the project is interested to interact with different stakeholders towards reaching its objectives. Experts from different backgrounds are therefore welcome to submit their application to become part of the pool of experts.

Submit your application now: [Link](#)

Important to know:

- Submitted applications are assessed by the ASSESS DHT consortium and the applicant is informed of the outcome
- If you are representing more than one of the four groups mentioned in the application, please select the one most suited group and focus your application on it. Applications from the same expert for multiple groups are not allowed.
- Engagement is not guaranteed. Depending on the needs of different consortium partners linked to their work in the project, ASSESS DHT will inform the pool of experts about opportunities for engagement.
- Engagement may be in different form, for example, participation in an online event (e.g. a two-hour webinar), provision of written feedback to a draft shared document, participation in an online interview, etc. It is not foreseen that experts will be required to travel physically.
- ASSESS DHT has reserved budget for remunerating experts. Specific budget lines are agreed based on the specific assignment at hand

Applications are evaluated following an [assessment scorecard](#).